

**FLUENT SPEECH, FORMED VOCABULARY, GRAMMAR AND
COMMUNICATION STYLE****Eshkobilova Ozoda Khalikulovna**

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Abstract: This article discusses the role of vocabulary, grammar, and communication in building fluency. Relying on pedagogical data and linguistic sources, the researcher clarified the problem on the basis of existing scientific and historical literature. The role of vocabulary, grammar and communication in the formation of fluent speech has been compared with specific approaches and theories.

Key words: speech, vocabulary, grammar, communication, children, approach, reasoning.

Аннотация: В этой статье обсуждается роль словарного запаса, грамматики и коммуникации в формировании беглой речи. Основываясь на педагогических данных и лингвистических источниках, исследователь уточнял проблему на основе имеющейся научной и исторической литературы. Роль лексики, грамматики и коммуникации в формировании беглой речи представляет собой сравнительный анализ конкретных подходов и теорий.

Ключевые слова: речь, лексика, грамматика, общение, дети, подход, рефлексия.

Introduction part

Fluency is a widespread concept that enables people to communicate and understand each other. Fluency cannot be separated from the world of thoughts: fluency is the fluency of thoughts, in which the child's logical thinking, the ability to reflect on what he perceives and express them correctly is manifested. Forming a fluent speech, changing its task is the result of the child's activity, which is becoming more

difficult, and it depends on the child's ability to communicate with others, the form of communication.

In preschool age, it develops in the process of communication and education. The formation of fluent speech takes place gradually from an early age. In the first seven years of children's life, it is necessary to pay special attention to the process of the emergence and development of speech as a means of conversation with the people around them. Fluent speech is important in everyone's life, and it performs three important functions: interpersonal, intra-individual and universal.

Language is a unique wealth of the nation, which we have always reflected orally and in writing. The noble possibilities of the language open up in the process of speech due to speech. If there is no speech, the limitless possibilities of the language will not be revealed. The sultan of words and ghazals, A. Navoi, explains the relationship between language and speech in this way: "Language is a tool of speech with so much honor. If the speech turns out to be inappropriate, it is in the interest of the language."

Therefore, no matter how excellent the language is, as long as it serves as a tool for speech, its strength and power are manifested in the process of speech. If language is an arrow, speech is a bow. The power of the arrow depends on the power of the bow¹.

Main part

It is known that language is considered the highest and main tool of human mind and activity, and it is not the language that distinguishes man from other creatures?! Therefore, the highest products of human mental activity, the fruits of thinking, are realized through language and speech. Language is a powerful tool through which the product of thought is brought to life.

Enriching the vocabulary with words - people, plants, food, clothes, furniture, pets and their children, with the names of toys, with the names of parts of things (shirt sleeves and collars; car bodies and wheels) is one of the biggest positive achievements in the development of human speech. is one. In games, teaching children to compare the expression of actions in words with their own expressive actions and the actions of toys is also one of the effective methods of speech development.

Improving the quality of the vocabulary is of the highest importance. This refers to the understanding and active use of phenomena such as antonymy (sharp-sharp, sharp-sharp), synonymy (sharp - sharpened, sharpened), multiple meaning (sharp knife, sharp pepper, sharp tongue). Children see things, natural phenomena, people's actions, learn to identify their diversity and commonality, and to express their meaning in speech using words, comparisons, specific verbs, similes (epithets) that are opposite or close to each other. Methods of matching synonyms or antonyms to a phrase show children that words have multiple meanings. Summarizing names (animals, dishes, transport, etc.) are formed based on the comparison of the functions of things.

Vocabulary development, education of the sound culture of speech, formation of grammatical correctness are closely related to mastering the methods of structuring fluent speech (connectors of sentences, lexical repetitions, means of linking with the help of synonyms; structure of description, description, reasoning).

All aspects of speech, formed on the basis of dialogic communication related to the performance of various functions, are directly related to the development of language consciousness, and for this, they need a certain form of communication of the child with adults, or rather, communication aimed not only at knowing the external world and other people, but also by understanding the language itself, its structure and operation. will need communication aimed at

Timely formation of the grammatical system of the child's language is the main condition for his full speech and general psychological development.

Results and discussions

The child acquires the grammatical system of the language during the development of knowledge in integral connection with mastering subject actions. The development of the grammatical system of preschool children's speech includes work on morphology (changing words according to stems, numbers, agreements), word formation (using special tools to form another word based on one word), syntax (forming simple and compound sentences).

It is necessary for the pedagogue to manage the children's grammatical development, first of all, both with the child (in the form of a dialogue) and with other children¹.

The development of the grammatical system in children - syntax, morphology, word formation - has its own special features, and the pedagogue should use various tools to improve them. Stimulating language games to master morphology and word formation; and for the development of syntax, the creation of motivation to express a broad opinion is an important factor.

For children of preschool age, it is necessary to consider two forms of speech - dialogic and monologic forms. Dialogue is characterized by the exchange of opinions of two or more speakers on a topic related to a situation. In the dialogue, all types of syntactically simple expressions, exclamations (please, request), and interrogative sentences are shown using prepositions. Language tools are strengthened by gestures and facial expressions. The teacher should create such a situation in which children can create a dialogue using various language tools - asking, answering, explaining, begging, biting, etc. let him face the necessity.

For this purpose, it is necessary to use the conversation on various topics related to the child's life in the family, in the preschool educational institution, his relations with friends and adults, his interests and impressions. It is in dialogue that the ability to listen to the interlocutor, ask questions, and answer based on the content develops. The mentioned qualifications and skills are also necessary for the development of monologic speech.

Cooperative activities are important for dialogic communication with peers. This activity is formed gradually. At first, children interpret the happenings and act nearby. In this situation, speech is stimulated by the presence of a peer and the opportunity to talk with him, and it performs the function of planning and organizing his activities, as well as establishing social communication.

Communication between children is mainly practical in nature. The dialogue is often carried out in such a way that the child responds with actions to the short bites of

the partner or expresses his attitude to the happening by means of non-verbal means. There are many folk games through which children learn to pay attention to each other, to recognize their friends by their voices, to notice the details of their appearance, and to communicate verbally.

It is recommended to use table games and printed ("loto", "domino") games to establish dialogue. Playing in pairs, children learn the methods of dialogical cooperation: taking turns, addressing each other politely, defending their point of view with evidence, coordinating their thoughts with their partner. Various types of speech tasks can be involved in such games as the basis of knowledge, for example: choosing words with a given sound, classifying acoustically and articulatory sounds close to each other, classifying generic names, telling a story together based on a series of pictures, etc.

The task of the preschool educational institution is to develop fluent conversational speech (dialogic speech) and monologic speech in children. The task of forming conversational speech is multifaceted. In preschool children, the ability to listen and understand the speech addressed to them, to listen to each other, to answer questions and to ask questions themselves, to give coherent answers on the topic of conversation is formed.

The difference between these two types of speech is determined by the type of logical communication of the sentence in the text. A monologue always reports on facts of existence that are temporally or causally related (relative to each other).

Conclusion

Listen to every word, don't rush. Don't speak without thinking. Think about every word you say, you won't regret what you said wrong **(from Kabusnoma)**.

It is known that language is the highest and main tool of the human mind. Because it is not the language that separates man from other creatures?! Therefore, the highest products of human mental activity, the fruits of thinking, are realized through language and speech. Language is a powerful tool that brings the product of thought to life.

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